

PREDICATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS WITH TO BE IN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRANSLATION WAYS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. *This article discusses about the linguistic peculiarities of linking verbs in English language. And also it studies the different ways of translation of linking verbs from English into Uzbek.*

Key words: *predicative, verb, linking verb, translation, grammatical relation.*

ПРЕДИКАТИВНЫЕ КОНСТРУКЦИИ С TO BE В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ И СПОСОБЫ ИХ ПЕРЕВОДА НА УЗБЕКСКИЙ ЯЗЫК

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются лингвистические особенности глаголов-связок в английском языке. А также изучает различные способы перевода глаголов-связок с английского на узбекский язык.*

Ключевые слова: *предикатив, глагол, глагол-связка, перевод, грамматическая связь.*

INTRODUCTION

In shaping the predicate, the differences of language systems become apparent stronger and multilaterally than in shaping the subject. This is stipulated by the capacity and importance of the given part of the sentence. Actually, the predicate bears greater number of grammatical relations than the subject does. The object itself, about which we are talking can reveal itself i.e. determine itself really only through actions and functions which are expressed by the predicate. The predicate connects the doer with the object and the modifiers of the action. That is why the predicate is factual center, which gravitates and gathers subgroups of all parts of the sentence. This happens in any language. But it is vividly seen in English, where one cannot omit any main parts of the sentence. Here it is indicative to compare Uzbek and English composite nominal predicate.

Mening akam - muhandis. - My brother is an engineer.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The predicate can be expressed by two types of verbs: verbs denoting action, and the verbs denoting existence and objective reality. The use of the verbs of the first group as a predicate does not differ greatly from the appropriate Uzbek verbs of action, that's why we shall not stop at the predicate, expressed by the verb of action. We shall consider the verbs of the second group, which includes to be and to have, in the meaning and use of which it is observed essential divergence in comparison with the appropriate Uzbek *bo'lmoq* and *ega bo'lmoq*.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Verb to be. English verb *to be* corresponds to Uzbek verb "*bo'lmoq*". In its main meaning "*bor bo'lmoq*" as it is well-known, verb "*bor bo'lmoq*" is used in the past and future tenses, but in present tense it is usually omitted. But in English it is obligatory to use the copula verb in the present tense too. Compare the sentences:

Men xonada edim.- I was in the room.

Men xonada bo'laman.- I'll be in the room.

Men xonadaman. – I am in the room.

DISCUSSION

Except the present tense (omitting copula verb in Uzbek and its obligatory presence in English – generally, it is formal circumstance, connected with the different structure of two languages), here the use and the meaning of 'to be' coincide with 'bo'lmoq' too. But the similarity exhausts here. Verb 'to be' is much richer in its potential semantic possibilities than Uzbek 'bo'lmoq'. Thus, depending on the context, it can obtain the meaning 'the state in the space', for example:

The book is on the table- Kitob stolda yotibdi.

The table is in the middle of the room- Stol hona o'rtasida turibdi.

The picture is on the wall- Sur'at devorda osilib turibdi.

Let's look at some more important of its numerous meanings:

1. "bo'lmoq, qatnashmoq"

She'll be here all the day. - U bu yerda butun kun davomida bo'ladi.

Kitty was here for the holidays. - Kiti bu yerga ta'til payti kelgan edi.

John was at the meeting, too. - Jon ham majlisda qatnashdi.

2. "sodir bo'lmoq, bor bo'lmoq"

It was only last year. - But faqat o'tgan yili sodir bo'lgan edi.

3. "teng bo'lmoq, tashkil etmoq"

Twice two is four. - Ikki kara ikki to'rtga teng.

4. "turadi (narxlar haqida)"

How much is the hat? – Bu shlyapa qancha turadi?

5. "iborat bo'lmoq"

The trouble was we did not know her address. - Muammo shundan iborat ediki biz uning manzilgohini bilmagan edik.

In perfect forms *to be* acquires the meaning "*tashrif buyurmoq, borib turmoq*".

I hear you've been to Switzerland this summer. – Mening eshitishimcha sen Shvetsariyaga borib kelibsan.

Has anyone been? - Kimdir kelgan edimi?

I've been for a walk. – Men sayr qilib kelgan edim.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, one can notice how wider English **to be** is used than Uzbek "bo'lmoq". This is very evident in a number of cases where Englishmen prefer composite nominal predicate, which consists of copula verb 'to be' and an adjective or participle I or II which have the meaning of appropriate verb, to simple verbal predicate.

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